

MODELS ARE VITAL TO PREDICT SOC DYNAMICS

Stringent validation of prediction models is needed at all scales based on time-series data.

NEED FOR UPDATED DATASET

Efforts to maintain datasets are imperative for accurate SOC projections and predictions.

DIVERSITY IS A VALUE ALSO IN MODELLING

Predictive models can be conceptually evaluated by comparing them to models designed for other goals.

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SOIL ORGANIC CARBON (SOC) MODELS NEED INDEPENDENT TIME-SERIES VALIDATION FOR RELIABLE PREDICTION

Validation

Most validations are based on field or laboratory experiments and only 23% are independent diachronic validated, which gives more accuracy to the model.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND SOIL MISSION OBJECTIVES

Supporting harmonised European soil information

understanding soil carbon sequestration and its contribution to climate change mitigation

Mission SOIL: Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL
framework programme

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